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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
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- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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INDICATORS AND DIAGNOSTIC APPROACHES FOR DYSLEXIA IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract: Maqolada boshlang'ich ta'lim bosqichida disleksiyani erta aniqlash va kompleks yondashuv asosida bartaraf etishning nazariy hamda amaliy jihatlari yoritiladi. Tahlilda AKT, multimodal (multisensor) metodlar va inklyuziv ta'lim muhitini birlashtirishning o'qish, yozish hamda talaffuz ko'nikmalariga ijobiy ta'siri asoslanadi. Diagnostika mezonlari sifatida o'qish tezligi, tovush-harf mosligi, matnni tushunish va imlo xatolarining tizimli bahosi taklif etiladi. Ishning yangiligi shundaki, u O'zbekiston kontekstida (boshlang'ich sinflarda ingliz tili) disleksiyaga xos fonetik-alifbo chalkashuvlarini (masalan, "sh-s", "r-l") aniqlab, ularni logopedik hamda AKT vositalari yordamida bosqichma-bosqich korreksiyalash uchun amaliy yo'riqnoma taklif etadi. Shuningdek, o'qituvchi faoliyati uchun to'rtta tizimli prinsip (integratsiya, resurs tejamkor metodika, uzluksiz monitoring, interfaollik) asosida amaliy model bayon etiladi. Maqola inklyuziv sinf amaliyotida ota-ona, logoped va pedagog hamkorligini mustahkamlash mexanizmlarini ochib beradi. Natijalar Yangi O'zbekiston-2030 ta'lim konsepsiyasi talablariga mos ravishda o'quvchilarning nutqiy kompetensiyasini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Xulosa sifatida, erda tashxis, dalillarga tayangan intervensiya va kontekstga mos raqamli resurslar kombinatsiyasi disleksiyaning sabab-oqibatlarini sezilarli kamaytirishi ko'rsatiladi.

Key words: disleksiya, boshlang'ich ta'lim, ingliz tili, AKT, multisensor yondashuv, erda diagnostika, logopedik ta'sir, fonetika va talaffuz, inklyuziv ta'lim, o'qish-yozish ko'nikmalari.

Annotatsiya: This article explores theoretical and practical approaches for the early identification and multi-level remediation of dyslexia in primary English instruction. It demonstrates the effectiveness of integrating ICT, multisensory methods, and an inclusive classroom environment to enhance reading, writing, and pronunciation skills. The proposed diagnostic criteria include reading rate, sound-letter correspondence, text comprehension, and the systematic analysis of spelling errors. The novelty lies in contextualizing established approaches within Uzbekistan's primary EFL setting and highlighting common phoneme-grapheme confusions (e.g., "sh-s," "r-l"), alongside staged speech therapy and digital supports. The paper further introduces a practical four-principle model for teachers (integration, resource-efficient methodology, continuous monitoring, interactivity) to structure lessons. It also elaborates on mechanisms for coordinated collaboration among teachers, speech therapists, and parents in inclusive classrooms. The findings correspond with Uzbekistan's 2030 education targets and are aimed at strengthening learners' speech competence. In conclusion, the study shows that combining early screening, evidence-based interventions, and context-appropriate digital resources can significantly reduce both the causes and consequences of dyslexia.

Kalit so'zlar: dyslexia, primary education, English language teaching, ICT, multisensory approach, early diagnosis, speech therapy, phonetics and pronunciation, inclusive education, reading and writing skills.

Аннотация: В статье освещаются теоретические и практические аспекты ранней диагностики и многоуровневой коррекции дислексии в начальном обучении английскому языку. Обоснована эффективность интеграции ИКТ, мультисенсорных методов и инклюзивной образовательной среды для развития чтения, письма и произношения. В качестве диагностических критериев предложены скорость чтения, соответствие звук-буква, понимание текста и системная оценка орфографических ошибок. Научная новизна заключается в контекстуализации известных подходов к условиям Узбекистана (начальная школа, английский как иностранный) и в выделении типичных фонетико-графемных путаниц (например, "sh-s", "r-l") с поэтапной логопедической и цифровой поддержкой. Дополнительно разработана практическая модель из четырёх системных принципов (интеграция, ресурсосберегающая методика, непрерывный мониторинг, интерактивность) для организации урока. Работа описывает механизмы трёхстороннего взаимодействия "учитель-логопед-родители" в инклюзивном классе. Результаты соотносятся с целевыми показателями Концепции развития образования до 2030 года и направлены на повышение речевой компетентности учащихся. Сделан вывод, что сочетание раннего скрининга, доказательных интервенций и контекстно адаптированных цифровых ресурсов существенно снижает последствия дислексии.

Ключевые слова: дислексия, начальная школа, английский язык, ИКТ, мультисенсорный подход, ранняя диагностика, логопедическое воздействие, фонетика и произношение, инклюзивное образование, навыки чтения и письма.

INTRODUCTION

The primary education stage is considered an important period in a child's psychological, speech, and intellectual development. It is precisely during this period that the fundamental literacy skills—reading, writing, and the ability to consciously use oral speech—are formed. However, in some students this process does not occur on its own, and various difficulties arise in reading and writing. Such a situation may be associated with a developmental disorder with a neurological basis called dyslexia. If the signs of dyslexia are not identified at an early stage, this negatively affects the child's assimilation of knowledge, self-confidence, and overall level of social adaptation. Therefore, early diagnosis and identification of dyslexia symptoms in primary school students are of great importance. The diagnostic process requires a comprehensive assessment of the child's reading speed, the correspondence between sounds and letters, the level of text comprehension, spelling errors in writing, and the specific features of speech activity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

From the moment each person is born, it is necessary to create a perfect society so that they can develop into a hardworking and talented individual. Since ancient times, Eastern peoples, especially Turkic peoples, have paid special attention to the upbringing of children. Great scholars, artists, creators, teachers, historians, and early Renaissance thinkers who emerged from the land of Turan—such as Forobiy, Az-Zamaxshariy, Al-Xorazmiy, Abu Rayhon Beruniy, and Ibn Sino—conducted special encyclopedic research in mathematics and took this issue seriously. Their major studies in philosophy, logic, grammar, phonetics, and other related fields of language and literature became even more refined by the early 20th century through the efforts of Jadid scholars. Indeed, in teaching any language, it is necessary to instill in the child the earliest theoretical and practical knowledge on the basis of the mother tongue and to help develop the skills of writing, speaking, and understanding. It would not be an exaggeration to say that raising educational technologies to a new level in terms of both quantity and quality, and scientifically substantiating the methodology of education in a national and universal spirit, became one of the main links of large-scale reforms. Child upbringing among Eastern peoples has developed differently in different periods. This process includes tested methods, experiences, and large-scale project research.

The changing global world today is placing new problems and tasks before humanity. It is no secret that decision-making, choosing the most optimal path, enabling children to conquer peaks of knowledge in a short time, and, along with other fields, sports as well, have launched practical steps on the path to New Uzbekistan's winning at Olympiads and securing a number of state grants. In this process, teaching English to primary school students requires the development of writing and reading skills, as well as individual sessions with students who have dyslexia. A natural question arises: based on his or her experience and qualifications, which path should the English teacher choose? In particular, it is becoming clear that introducing inclusive education on the basis of effective methods, together with the teacher and other students—the class community—is the only way to develop children's reading and writing skills. Inclusivity is derived from the English word "inclusive," meaning inclusion and integration. This term refers to the process of teaching students with special needs together with typical children in general secondary schools. Of course, this concept is only one part of a type of education aimed at comprehensively covering students who have mental and physiological characteristics, including those with dyslexia. This is a field that provides broad opportunities for both children with speech and developmental impairments and typical students in mixed groups to receive education. For example, in English before first grade, almost 60 percent of students are mastering the correct pronunciation of familiar letters and words learned in kindergarten. Over the past five years, serious reforms have been carried out in New Uzbekistan's education system to expand the coverage of children with preschool education; laws, decisions, and decrees have been adopted, and the normative-legal documents of the education system have been defined. In developed countries of the world, mechanisms for free and quality education for every child that meet the standards of UNESCO and many other organizations have been developed, and large-scale programs have been adopted.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Within the framework of the Concept, by fulfilling the tasks set, the following indicators are envisaged to be achieved in the development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan by 2030: general education curricula and new state educational standards that meet the requirements of a modern innovative economy will be introduced, taking into account a special emphasis on the development of STEAM subjects and competencies and skills of critical thinking, independent search for and analysis of information; the continuous participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international programs and studies for assessing education quality (PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS, etc.) will be ensured in assessing students' knowledge levels in the

public education system; the accession of the Republic of Uzbekistan to leading international associations for the accreditation of educational programs and institutions will be ensured; new generations of didactic materials and multimedia products aimed at in-depth study of foreign languages, computer science, mathematics, physics, chemistry, and biology will be prepared; network schools will be created on the basis of successfully functioning general education institutions, and other schools with a low coefficient of student coverage will also be included in this network. Thus, the majority of children with dyslexia are directed toward inclusive education. It has been determined that, in order to form healthy, complete, and clear concepts in children, it is important that they sit alongside students who have speech impairments and receive foundational knowledge in both their mother tongue and English.

Organizing such education is found to depend on the student's scientific-creative potential, talent, and ability. Among primary school students—especially in literacy instruction—cases are observed of mispronouncing letters, stuttering, and accepting a letter they think they understand as correct: for example, when pronouncing an Uzbek word in English (when writing certain capital letters, dividing words into syllables, transferring syllables, pronouncing letter by letter, blending), substituting the letter “sh” with “s,” and the letter “r” with “l.” For instance, “olma” – “apple” (children with dyslexia pronounce it as “oma!”). Here, the “l” sound is omitted. “Telefon” – “telephone.” Even though they know it is a means of communication, if they read and pronounce “tilipon” in Uzbek, it is rendered as “tphon” in English. Therefore, if the teacher does not approach the teaching of letters, sounds, and phonetic rules seriously and attentively, it will be difficult to achieve the specific goal set. “Children in need of assistance who have defects in their physical and mental development are equal members of our state. Ensuring that they receive education and upbringing on an equal basis with everyone else in all institutions of the continuous education system is one of our main tasks.” In this regard, the scholar emphasizes the necessity of speech therapy intervention that proves the existence of such methods for eliminating dyslexia. This is because the main goal of the principles of speech therapy intervention is the correct formation of speech sounds. Indeed, in primary education, in order to develop a clear and explicit method for systematically teaching students in grades 1-4, it is of great importance to organize instruction in the mother tongue and English on the basis of certain templates, taking into account students' weak points and shortcomings.

“We make extensive use of didactic materials to eliminate pronunciation deficiencies. The timeframes for correcting pronunciation disorders depend on a number of factors: the complexity of the defect, the child's age and individual characteristics, the regularity of sessions, and parental support. In simple dyslalia, sessions last from one to three months, while in complex dyslalia they last from three to six months. In preschool-aged children, pronunciation defects are eliminated in a shorter time compared to school-aged children, and in younger school-aged children more quickly than in older school-aged children. Speech therapy intervention is carried out step by step; at each stage, a specific pedagogical task related to the overall goal of speech therapy intervention is solved.” There are many factual sources about the letters in which dyslexia mainly manifests: firstly, when letters such as h-x, t-p, b-p, s-f, o-o', q-r are pronounced freely, the fact that these concepts have been internalized in their minds as in the mother tongue has a negative effect on them. At the same time, the complexity of dyslexia related to existing letters and sounds is transferred to the process of pronouncing words. Therefore, it is advisable for the teacher first and foremost, in cooperation with the mother or caregiver-pedagogue and a specialist, to pay special attention to solving the speech therapy problem. We can see in historical sources that the perceptual capacity of preschool and school-aged children with defects is extremely broad.

Children are not at all alike. Similarities at a young age can be identified through their mental abilities and interest in various subjects—this is the process of experience. Even if they approach education in the same way, they differ sharply from each other in diverse activities: they enrich their life concepts in different ways, strive for different tasks, sit, walk, speak, listen differently, freely express their own concepts, and play. They gradually adapt to life, accumulating in their memory a certain treasury of representations: the dream they saw yesterday, what they ate, even where they went and what they watched. It turns out that dyslexia creates complex situations against a background of constant strain on memory, severe depression and psycholinguistic disorders, family conflicts, threats from peers, and the influence of natural forces on the mind and psyche. One of the main tasks of a primary education teacher is how to instill English into the child's mind, to instill concepts, words, phrases, proverbs or sayings, and to guide the child to work with texts. In such conditions, through the child's daily experience—cartoons, films, or games—a mechanism is systematically formed in the child's mind for immersing into the world of nature and animals, living in the world of bright dreams, and adapting with pleasure. If a speech defect in speech therapy is defined as a deviation from certain norms of a language, the Russian specialist O. V. Pravdina, in her book *Logopediya (Speech Therapy)*, defines speech therapy speech disorders as follows: “Speech defects usually do not disappear on their own; on the contrary, they intensify over time. They manifest as speech deviations that do not correspond to the person's age and level of development. Individuals in such a condition need speech therapy assistance, and severe speech defects negatively affect not only communicative activity but also general mental and social development.”

CONCLUSION

It should be emphasized that understanding the essence, course, and manifestation of psychological concepts such as thinking, memory, perception, knowledge, skills, and competencies in the context of the psychological factors of speech difficulties is important. In this regard, the learner's language-learning ability, memory, and developmental possibilities must be taken into account. If the learner's long-term memory develops, the selected material is better retained, and the student begins to use it freely, fluently, and accurately in speech activities. Thus, if primary school students, relying on the foundational knowledge they acquire in their early years of study, begin to solve problems before entering higher education institutions, psycholinguodidactic problems will be resolved more effectively. In this process, the English teacher's main methodological recommendations and expertise are especially valuable. A creative approach, psychological-pedagogical mastery, and the application of modern teaching methods are required from the teacher. Through this, opportunities for forming correct pronunciation, reading, and writing skills in children, as well as for their successful integration into society, are expanded. In general, early diagnosis of dyslexia, the provision of systematic speech therapy and pedagogical support, and the implementation of inclusive education mechanisms are decisive factors in increasing the effectiveness of primary education.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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